

The Effect of Marketing Mix and Brand Image on Purchase Decisions of Fashion Online Products

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Abstract

This study discusses the effect of marketing mix consisting of product, price and promotion, as well as brand image on purchasing decisions for Ukhti and Munira products at online store La Vieta ButiQ in Jember. The purpose of this study is to test and analyze the effect of product, price and promotion on purchasing decisions and brand image as intervening variable. The respondents analyzed included 100 online consumers Ukhti and Munira. The analytical method used is *Path Analysis* and Sobel Test with *accidental sampling technique*. The results of this study indicate that product and promotion have a significant effect on brand image, price does not affect brand image. Product, price and promotion have a significant effect on purchasing decisions, but brand image has no influence on purchasing decisions. Brand image does not mediate the influence of product, price and promotion on the purchase decisions for Ukhti and Munira products.

Keywords: Product; price; promotion; brand image; purchase decision.

1. Introduction

The development of technology is now very rapid, especially in the field of internet, even marketing is currently done through the internet online. The rapid development of internet access has a positive impact on the world of business and marketing (Tjiptono, 2016). The development of the internet, especially social media which feels very fast indeed makes lifestyle and consumer behavior also change, including consumer behavior in making decisions to buy a product. Consumers as product users are increasingly smart in choosing products, so producers must use appropriate marketing strategies to attract consumers to buy their products (Dimiyati, 2014). One of them is by using a marketing mix or marketing mix strategy, which consists of product, price, promotion and distribution channels (Malau, 2017). Consumers will also determine their choice to buy a product that has a good brand image because a strong and good brand image will determine the purchase decision of a product by consumers (Sangadji and Sopiah, 2013). The existence of social media, the public easily see a variety of product offerings and services offered, including information and offers around the world of fashion. The number of new hijab brands that have sprung up from time to time, and with quite fierce competition in the fashion sector and the proliferation of online stores on social media, consumers are faced with so many choices for buying hijab products they want.

Ukhti and Munira are one of the Muslim fashion brands in Indonesia that are developing and helped to enliven the Muslim fashion market in Indonesia. Ukhti and Munira are also one of the brands that have succeeded in marketing their products through social media, namely Facebook, even marketing abroad. The Ukhti brand that was founded in 2008 was a Muslim fashion company that carried out its marketing strategy through offline marketers, through agency distribution channels, namely distributors, agents, and resellers, before the internet boom, and at one time the Ukhti brand was almost bankrupt, because it was left behind by the network the marketer. In addition, with the increasing number of new Muslim

fashion brands that have sprung up, but then the Ukhti brand can bounce back with a new marketing concept that is through social media Facebook. Previously, the design of Ukhti was a boss made from a t-shirt, so in 2016, Ukhti came back with a new design concept, the robe - robe which is currently a trend. The Ukhti brand also improves the quality of its products by using convenient materials, affordable prices and promotion through Facebook social media.

How Ukhti and Munira Brands can rise again and compete amid the rise of many emerging Muslim fashion brands, with marketing mix strategies, improving product quality, product design, adjusting prices and promoting their products online, this will be discussed in this study. As well as how Ukhti and Munira strengthen their brand image in the face of new brands offering the same products, the same promotion methods, but at prices lower than those offered by Ukhti and Munira, and making consumers choose and decide to buy the Ukhti Munira Brand. Based on these phenomena, the problem formulated in this study is "How the influence of product, price and promotion on purchasing decisions and the role of brand image as an intervening variable". While the purpose of this study is to determine and analyze the effect of product, price and promotion variables on purchasing decisions through brand image as an intervening variable. This research was conducted on online consumers who have shopped Ukhti and Munira products on the GForce team only, who are in the management of La Vieta ButiQ.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Product

Setyaningrum, Udaya, Efendi, (2015), Product is a collection of physical, psychological, service and symbolic attributes that are made to satisfy the needs and desires of customers. Assauri, (2017) Product is a product or service produced to be used by consumers to meet needs and provide satisfaction. Malau (2017), states that product attributes are, *product quality, variety, design, features, brand names, packaging, size, services, warranties, returns*. These product attributes will be considered by consumers in making decisions about purchasing a brand or product category attached to the product or being part of the product itself. The product attributes used in this study are product quality, product design and product variants.

2.2. Price

Priansa (2017), Price is the amount of value exchanged by consumers for the benefit of owning or using a product whose value is determined by the buyer and seller through bargaining or is determined by the seller for one price the same for all buyers. Setyaningrum, Udaya, Efendi (2015), price is the sum of all values given by consumers to obtain *benefits* for the ownership or use of a product or service. In this study the price offered by Ukhti Munira is based on the buyer's perception of value. The indicator for price is affordable prices, prices in accordance with the budget, prices according to product quality, prices are able to compete with other brands on the market.

2.3. Promotion

Priansa (2017), Promotion is an element that is used to inform and persuade the market about new products or services to companies, advertisements, personal sales, sales promotions and publicity. This study uses indicators for promotion namely Advertising, Personal Selling, and Sales Promotion.

2.4. Brand Image

Assauri, (2017), Brand Image is a name, term, sign or symbol and a combination of two or more elements, which are intended to identify goods or services from a seller or seller group and distinguish them from competing products. The components of the brand image used in this study are, the brand is well known, the brand is easy to remember by consumers, trusted brands, brands have a good reputation, brand appearance and logo, brand benefits, brand guarantees.

2.5. Purchase decision

Priansa (2017), purchasing decisions are processes that cannot be separated from the nature of consumer involvement with the product. The stages of the purchasing decision process according to Kotler and Armstrong (2012), consist of:

- 1) Problem Recognition, purchasing decisions begin with the needs and desires of consumers
- 2) Information Search after consumers realize the need for a particular product, then the consumer is looking for information
- 3) Evaluation of Alternatives, after information is obtained, consumers evaluate various alternative choices in meeting those needs.
- 4) Purchase Decisions, the actual purchase is the final result of the search and evaluation that has been done.
- 5) Post Purchase Evaluation

Kotler and Armstrong (2012) also stated that for consumers, actually purchasing is not just an action (for example because of a product), but consists of several actions which are interrelated. Dimensions of purchase decisions used in this study are the Product Choices, Prices, Promotions, Brand Choices, Seller Choices, Number of Purchases, Time of Purchase, References from others.

3. Research Methods

The population in this study were all customers who had shopped at La Vieta ButiQ who purchased Muslim clothing specifically for the Ukhti and Jilbab Munira brands, totaling approximately 800 customers, all of whom were female. The population of approximately 800 customers is taken from La Vieta ButiQ sales data for 2018 - 2019. The basis of sampling according to Roscoe (Sugiyono, 2017) which in this study uses 5 variables (independent + dependent), the minimum sample size is $10 \times 5 = 50$, but in this study used a sample of 100 customers, all of whom were women with an age range of 20-40 years and above, the average level of education S1 or Bachelor degree, which was dominated by housewives, with incomes between 3 million to 5 million per month, and have been subscribed for 6 months to 1 year.

The sampling method used in this study uses a non probability sampling method with incidental sampling technique (Sugiyono, 2017).

Data collection methods used in this study were conducted by questionnaire, indirect interview, observation and literature study. The measurement scale used is the Likert Scale with a range of 1 to 5 points. Data analysis method used is Path Analysis and Sobel Test Technique.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Information :

X1 = Product Y1 = Brand Image
X2 = Price Y2 = Purchase Decision
X3 = Promotion

Hypothesis

The hypotheses in this study are :

- H1.1 : Product influences brand image
- H1.2 : Price affects Brand Image
- H1.3 : Promotion influences brand image
- H.2 : Brand Image influences the Purchasing Decision
- H3.1 : The product has a direct effect on the Purchasing Decision
- H3.2 : Prices directly influence the Purchase Decision
- H3.3 : Promotion has a direct effect on Purchasing Decisions
- H4.1 : Products influence Purchasing Decisions through Brand Image
- H4.2 : Price influences Purchasing Decisions through Brand Image
- H4.3 : Promotion influences Purchasing Decisions through Brand Image.

The path analysis formula in this study are:

- 1) The influence of product independent variables (X1), price (X2) and promotion (X3) on brand image (Y1). The formula is:

$$Y1 = a + b1X1 + b2X2 + b3X3 + e1$$

- 2) The *direct influence* of product independent variables (X1), price (X2), promotion (X3) and brand image (Y1) on purchasing decisions (Y2). The formula is:

$$Y2 = a + b1X1 + b2X2 + b3X3 + b3Y1 + e2$$

- 3) The *indirect effect*, product, price and promotion (X) on purchasing decisions (Y2) through brand image (Y1). The formula is:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{The direct effect of X1 to Y2} &= p1 \\ \text{The indirect effect of X1 to Y1 to Y2} &= p2 \times p3 \\ \text{Total Effect (Total Effect)} &= p1 + (p2 \times p3) \end{aligned}$$

Sobel Test

According to Ghazali (2016), Testing the mediation hypothesis can be done by a procedure developed by Sobel (1982) and known as the Sobel test. The Sobel test is carried out by testing the strength of the indirect influence X to Y2 through Y1.

Sobel Test Formula:

$$sab = \sqrt{b^2sa^2 + a^2sb^2 + sa^2sb^2}$$

To test the significance of the indirect effect, it is necessary to calculate the *t* value of the *ab* coefficient with the following formula:

$$t = \frac{ab}{sab}$$

This calculated *t value* is compared with the *t* table value .

The evaluation criteria are:

- 1) If the value of *t* arithmetic > value of *t* table then it can be concluded the influence of mediation occurs.
- 2) If the value of *t* arithmetic <value of *t* table then it can be concluded that there is no mediating effect.

4. Results

4.1. Test of Equation of the Double Regression

First Equation Test for Multiple Regression

Table 1: Results of the first equation test for multiple regression

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std.Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	1.253	2.571		0.488	0.627
Product	0.504	0.085	0.420	5.908	0.000
Price	0.234	0.137	0.116	1.711	0.090
Promotion	0.862	0.143	0.441	6.044	0.000

a. Dependent Variable: brand image

Source : 2019 SPSS calculation results

$$\begin{aligned} Y1 &= a + b1X1 + b2X2 + b3X3 + e1 \\ e1 &= \sqrt{(1 - 0.733)} = 0.517 \\ Y1 &= 1.253 + 0.420(X1) + 0.116(X2) + 0.441(X3) + 0.517 \end{aligned}$$

Based on the *Coefficients output* table, note that:

- 1) The product variable regression coefficient (X1) of 0.420 is positive, the value of Sig. Product variable (X1) is 0.000 smaller than or <0.05, which means the Product variable **has a significant effect** on the Brand Image variable (Y1).
- 2) Value of the regression coefficient variable price (X2) of 0.116 is positive, Value Sig. Price variable (X2) of 0.090 is greater than or > 0.05 which means that the variable price has **no significant effect** on the Brand Image variable.
- 3) The promotional variable regression coefficient (X3) of 0.441 is positive, the Sig. Promotion variable (X3) of 0.000 <0.05 which means that the Promotion variable **has a significant effect** on the Brand Image variable.

In addition to the results of the determinant coefficient table below:

Table 2: R Square table

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.856 ^a	0.733	0.725	2.514

a. Predictors: (Constant), promotions, prices, products

Source : 2019 SPSS calculation results

Second Equation Test for Multiple Regression

Table 3: Results of the second equation test for multiple regression

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	2,268	3,705		0.612	0.542
Product	0.366	0.143	0.259	2.551	0.012
Price	0.421	0.200	0.178	2.108	0.038
Promotion	0.751	0.241	0.326	3.111	0.002
Brand Image	0.166	0.147	0.141	1.128	0.262

a. Dependent Variable: purchasing decision

Source: 2019 SPSS calculation results

$$Y_2 = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + Y_1 + e_2$$

$$e_2 = \sqrt{(1 - 0.606)} = 0.628$$

$$Y_2 = 2.268 + 0.259(X_1) + 0.178(X_2) + 0.326(X_3) + 0.141(Y_1) + 0.628$$

Based on the *Coefficients output* table, it is known that:

- 1) The product variable regression coefficient (X1) of 0.259 is positive, the value of Sig. Product variable (X1) is 0.012 smaller than or <0.05 which means the Product variable **has a significant effect** on the Purchase Decision variable (Y2).
- 2) Value of the regression coefficient variable price (X2) of 0.178 is positive, Value Sig. Price variable (X2) of 0.038 is smaller than or <0.05, which means that the variable price **has a significant effect** on the variable Purchase Decision.
- 3) The value of the regression coefficient for promotion variable (X3) of 0.326 is positive, the Sig. Promotion variable (X3) of 0.002 <0.05 which means that the Promotion variable **has a significant effect** on the Purchase Decision variable.
- 4) The value of the regression coefficient for brand image (Y1) of 0.141 is positive, Sig. Brand Image variable is 0.262 > 0.05 which means that Brand Image variable **has no significant effect** on Purchasing Decisions.

In addition to the results of the determinant coefficient table below :

Table 4 : R Square table

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.779 ^a	0.606	0.590	3.619

a. Predictors: (Constant), brand image, price, products, promotions

Source : 2019 SPSS calculation results

4.2. Mediation Test

Mediation test is used to find out in detail the direct and indirect effects of the independent variable on the dependent variable, and the effect of the mediating variable on the intervening variable.

4.2.1. Product Mediation Test Against Purchasing Decisions Through Brand Image

Figure 2: Mediation Test Results

Based on the results of the first equation and the second equation of multiple regression, it is known that the product variable (X1) has a direct influence on the purchase decision of 0.259. While the product variable gives an indirect effect on the Purchase Decision variable (Y2) through the Brand Image variable (Y1) calculated by multiplying its indirect coefficient $(0.420 \times 0.141) + 0.259 = 0.318$. The effect of mediation is calculated by means of the Sobel Test:

$$\begin{aligned}
 sab &= \sqrt{p^3 sa^2 + p^2 sb^2 + sa^2 sb^2} \\
 &= \sqrt{(0.141^2 * 0.085^2) + (0.420^2 * 0.147^2) + (0.085^2 * 0.147^2)} \\
 &= \sqrt{0.004112} = 0.064
 \end{aligned}$$

Value the *t* count is:

$$t = \frac{ab}{sab} = \frac{0.420 * 0.141}{0.064} = \frac{0.059}{0.064} = 0.923$$

The *t* value of the product variable is 0.923 smaller than *t* table 1.98 so it can be concluded that **there is no mediating effect**, which means the brand image as an intervening variable for the product on purchasing decisions, is **not proven**.

4.2.2. Mediation Test Prices Against Purchasing Decisions Through Brand Image

Figure 3: Mediation Test Results

Based on Figure, it is known that the variable Price (X2) gives a direct influence on purchasing decisions of 0.178. While the price variable gives an indirect effect on the Purchase Decision variable (Y2) through the Brand Image variable (Y1) calculated by multiplying its indirect coefficient $(0.116 \times 0.141) + 0.178 = 0.194$. The effect of mediation is calculated by means of the Sobel Test as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} sab &= \sqrt{p^3sa^2 + p^2sb^2 + sa^2sb^2} \\ &= \sqrt{(0.141^2 * 0.137^2) + (0.116^2 * 0.147^2) + (0.137^2 * 0.147^2)} \\ &= \sqrt{0.001070} = 0.0327 \end{aligned}$$

Value *the t* count is:

$$t = \frac{ab}{sab} = \frac{0.116 * 0.141}{0.0327} = \frac{0.016356}{0.0327} = 0.500$$

The *t* value of the price variable is 0.500 smaller than *t* table 1.98, so it can be concluded that **there is no mediating effect**, which means the brand image as an intervening variable for prices on purchasing decisions, is **not proven**.

4.2.3. Promotional Mediation Test Against Purchasing Decisions Through Brand Image

Figure 4: Mediation Test Results

Based on the results of the first equation and the second equation of multiple regression, it is known that the Promotion variable (X3) gives a direct influence on purchasing decisions of 0.326. While the promotion variable gives an indirect effect on the Purchase Decision variable (Y2) through the Brand Image variable (Y1) calculated by multiplying its indirect coefficient $(0.441 \times 0.141) + 0.326 = 0.388$. The effect of mediation is calculated by means of the Sobel Test as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} sab &= \sqrt{p^3sa^2 + p^2sb^2 + sa^2sb^2} \\ &= \sqrt{(0.141^2 * 0.143^2) + (0.441^2 * 0.147^2) + (0.143^2 * 0.147^2)} \\ &= \sqrt{0.005052} = 0.071 \end{aligned}$$

Value *the t* count is:

$$t = \frac{ab}{sab} = \frac{0.441 * 0.141}{0.071} = \frac{0.062181}{0.071} = 0.876$$

The *t* value of the promotion variable is 0.876 smaller than *t* table 1.98, so it can be concluded that **there is no mediating effect**, which means the brand image as an intervening variable for promotion on purchasing decisions, is **not proven**.

Table 5 : Direct, Indirect, and Mediation Effects

Influence of Variables	Coefficient Value (β)	Through Y1	Sobel Test results	t table	Information
X1 \rightarrow Y2	0.259				Significant
X 1 \rightarrow Y2 through Y1		$0.259 + (0.420 \times 0.141) = 0.318$	0.923	1.98	Not mediate
X 2 \rightarrow Y2	0.178				Significant
X 2 \rightarrow Y2 through Y1		$0.178 + (0.116 \times 0.141) = 0.194$	0.500	1.98	Does not mediate
X 3 \rightarrow Y2	0.326				Significant
X 3 \rightarrow Y2 through Y1		$0.326 + (0.441 \times 0.141) = 0.388$	0.876	1.98	Does not mediate
Y1 \rightarrow Y2	0.141				Not significant
X1 \rightarrow Y1	0.420				Significant
X2 \rightarrow Y1	0.116				Not significant
X3 \rightarrow Y1	0.441				Significant

Source: 2019 SPSS calculation results

5. Discussion

The results of the path analysis test showed the product coefficient value on purchasing decisions amounted to 0.259, while the total indirect value was 0.318 and the t-value based on the sobel test was $0.923 < t$ table of 1.98, thus the brand image was not a intervening variable.

The value of the price coefficient on purchasing decisions is 0.178, while the total indirect value is 0.194 and the t-test value based on the sobel test is $0.500 < t$ table that is 1.98, so brand image is not an intervening variable.

The promotion coefficient value on purchasing decisions is 0.326, while the total indirect value is 0.388 and the t-test value based on the sobel test is $0.874 < t$ table, that is 1.98, so brand image is not an intervening variable.

Figure 5: Mediation Test Results

Effect of Product, Price and Promotion on Brand Image

The results of this study indicate that the product has a positive and significant effect on Brand Image. Products consisting of three items namely product quality, product design and product variants received good responses from customer respondents Ukhti and Munira. The average respondent gave a good and positive assessment of the Ukhti and

Munira products, the better the product quality, diverse product designs and many product variants, the more the brand image of the Ukhti and Munira products will be further enhanced. This is also in line with research by Reven and Ferdinand (2017) which states that product design and product quality have a positive and significant effect on the brand image of Nesty Collection products. This is also supported by Rangkuti (2009), who in his book states that consumers see the brand as an important part, by giving a brand name can add value to the product.

The price variable shows the result that price does not significantly influence brand image. This is because consumers will look for products of good quality at more affordable prices, consumers also choose clothes based on their needs and comfort so that any price will still be purchased regardless of the brand. On average respondents gave good responses and perceptions of the prices of Ukhti and Munira products, but in fact it was not enough to influence the brand image of the Ukhti and Munira brand. The results of this study are not in line with research conducted by Anandia and Santoso (2015), which states that price has a positive and significant effect on Brand Image. In the study, it was said that the more positive the consumer's perception of the price of adidas shoes, the higher the brand image. According to (Tjiptono and Diana, 2016), a strong brand image should be able to provide marketing excellence in various marketing activities, one of which is related to price.

Promotion variable shows that promotion has a significant effect on brand image, even the biggest effect compared to the other two variables. Promotions conducted by the Ukhti and Munira brands can continuously improve the brand image of the brand. Consumers will remember a product that is advertised continuously. The results of this study are also supported by research conducted by Rahman and Santoso (2015), which states that promotion is proven to have a significant positive effect on the brand image of the Semarang Jolly Roger distribution. Whereas according to (Tjiptono and Diana, 2016), a strong brand image is able to provide marketing excellence in a variety of marketing activities which include related to marketing communication, in the form of a stronger response to brand advertising, more positive product evaluations, consumers are easier to remember brand advertising, attention to brand marketing communication is higher. Promotion is also used to keep the brand in people's minds. (Setyaningrum, Udaya, Efendi, 2015).

Effect of Brand Image on Purchasing Decisions

The results of this study indicate that brand image has no significant effect on purchasing decisions. This happens because the brand image of Brand Ukhti and Munira is not too strong, so it does not affect the brand's image on purchasing decisions. Also due to the increasing number of new brands that have sprung up, so consumers are faced with a large number of brand choices, especially in the online world that more and more new brands are popping up. This is not in line with research conducted by Efendi, Widyaningrum, Imamah (2017), which states that brand image has the most dominant influence on the repurchase of Elzatta products, which means that the decision to repurchase Elzatta products in Surabaya is strongly influenced by the brand image of that brand. According to Kotler and Armstrong (2012), for consumers, actually purchasing is not just an action (for example because of a product), but consists of several actions that are interrelated to one another as a choice of brand. Meanwhile, according to Priansa (2017), Consumers must decide which brands to buy, each brand has its own differences.

Effect of Product, Price and Promotion on Purchasing Decisions

The results of this study indicate that there is a significant positive effect of the product on the buying decisions of the Ukhti and Munira brands. Products from the Ukhti and Munira brands that have good product quality, diverse designs and many variants make it a reason for consumers to decide to buy Ukhti and Munira products. Based on research by Hanif and Rachma (2017), it states that product quality and product design have a significant effect on purchasing decisions. However this is not in line with research conducted by Swandaya (2017) and Wahid (2017) which states that the product has no significant effect on purchasing decisions. According to Priansa (2017), consumers take the decision to buy a product or use their money by looking at the superiority of the product in the form of the level of quality expected by consumers for the products they need from a variety of product choices.

The price variable shows that the price has a significant effect on purchasing decisions, but the effect is not too large. Consumers accept the price offer set by the Ukhti and Munira brands but the offer is not in accordance with the wishes of the consumers, so Ukhti Munira needs to evaluate the pricing policy strategy adopted to make it more affordable for Ukhti and Munira consumers. In research conducted by Krisna. H (2016), price has a dominant influence on purchasing decisions, because customers see price elements including prices offered in accordance with product quality, product prices offered at the Arrival Mode Jember Clothing Shop are affordable with the purchasing power of consumers, cheaper and able to compete with other store. But this is not in line with research conducted by Swandaya (2017), which mentions that prices do not significantly influence purchasing decisions on Mutiara Fashion consumers, because respondents from Mutiara Fashion do not prioritize the price of the product to be purchased, respondents will only buy if interested in promotion offered. According to Abdullah and Tantri (2017), price changes will affect consumers, consumers do not always take direct interpretation of price changes, both price reductions and price increases. Consumer reactions to price changes also vary according to their perceptions.

Promotion variable shows that promotion has a significant effect on purchasing decisions. The average respondent is steady in buying Ukhti and Munira because the promotions offered are attractive, and respondents respond well to the advertisements offered by Ukhti and Munira especially when there is a discount or sale and when there is a launch of a new product. In a study conducted by Swandaya (2017), Hidayah (2016), Efendi, Widyaningrum, Imamah (2017), Rahman and Santoso (2015), which mentioned that the Promotion variable significantly influenced consumer purchasing decisions. But this is not in line with Wahid's research (2017), which states that promotion does not significantly influence purchasing decisions, respondents from Wahid's research did not pay too much attention to promotion as one of the considerations in purchasing decisions because without promotion even consumers will still come because consumers have become a loyal customer of the product. According to (Setyaningrum, Udaya, Efedi, 2015) Promotion is an attempt to influence other parties.

Effect of Products, Prices and promotions on Purchasing Decisions through Imagery Brand

The results of this study indicate that brand image is not an intervening variable for product variables on purchasing decisions. Ukhti and Munira products that have gone through quality improvement, updated designs that are more modern and trendy following the changing times and more diverse variants apparently have not been able to improve the brand image of the Ukhti Munira brand. Consumers buy Ukhti and Munira products only because their products are of good quality and there are many variants. This is not in line with research conducted by Rahman and Santoso (2015), and Anandia and Santoso (2015), which mentioned that products consisting of product quality and product design had a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions with brand image as an intervening variable. According to Rangkuti (2009), consumers buy products with brands that promise the most product attributes that suit their needs and desires.

The price variable shows that brand image is not an intervening variable for the price of a purchasing decision. The price of Munira's Ukhti product does not affect consumer purchasing decisions through its brand image, this is because the perception of prices on the Ukhti and Munira brands is not in accordance with consumers' perceptions so that the decision to buy Ukhti and Munira's products does not affect. This is not in line with research conducted by Anandia and Santoso (2015), which mentions that prices have a positive effect on purchasing decisions through brand image. According to Priansa (2017), consumers always consider prices in accordance with the quality and benefits of the product. If a product with a good brand image, good quality and great benefits, then consumers will not hesitate to spend high costs to get and buy the product.

Promotion variable shows that brand image is not an intervening variable for promotion of purchasing decisions. Promotions conducted by Ukhti and Munira marketers have not been able to improve the brand image of the Ukhti Munira brand, only introduce the Ukhti Munira brand and influence consumers' decisions to buy Ukhti Munira products through advertisements carried out on social media due to discount and sale promotions. This is not in line with research Rahman and Santoso (2015), stated that brand image is proven to mediate promotion of the stability of purchasing decisions. According to Rangkuti (2009), consumers sometimes buy something different from what was previously intended. Consumers may have chosen a brand that they like, but it can change because of sales promotions from competing brands.

6. Recommendation

Based on the research results promotion variables have a significant effect on brand image variables and on purchasing decisions, and the effect is greatest among other variables. However, the promotion variable does not affect the purchase decision through the brand image variable as its intervening variable. It is suggested for companies from Ukhti and Munira to conduct more varied and more innovative promotions that are not only in the form of discounts or sales, but can also be in the form of consumer involvement to promote the Ukhti and Munira brands so that they can introduce the Ukhti and Munira brands more broadly and more improve the image of the Ukhti and Munira brand, and can form consumer loyalty in the Ukhti and Munira brand. The selection of promotional media also needs to be considered, if currently only using promotions on Facebook and Instagram social media, in the future it can be considered other promotional media such as websites, promotions in print media or can also follow events and become sponsorships at an event. Further researchers are advised to include other marketing mixes such as distribution channels or places, people, processes and physical evidence in their research. It is also recommended to examine the variables of customer satisfaction and customer loyalty.

7. Conclusion

Based on the results of the analysis of the independent variables and the dependent variables in this study it can be concluded that:

Product and promotion variables have positive and significant effect on brand image variables. It can be concluded that the better the product quality, diverse product designs and many product variants, the more the brand image of the Ukhti

and Munira products will be further enhanced. It can also be concluded that the promotion carried out continuously will be able to improve the brand image of a brand, consumers will remember a product that is advertised continuously, as is done by the Ukhti and Munira brands. While the price variable does not significantly influence the brand image variable. It can be concluded that, price can have a positive effect on brand image, but it can also have no effect on brand image, because for consumers, the important thing is how to get goods in accordance with the actual price.

The brand image variable does not significantly influence the purchase decision variable. It can be concluded that, brand image can influence consumer purchasing decisions, if the brand image of the product is strong enough in consumers' memories, but brand image can not influence consumers' decision to buy a product because consumers decide to buy products in the brand they like best.

Product, price, and promotion variables have positive and significant influence on purchasing decision variables. It can be concluded that the product can have a positive influence on consumer purchasing decisions. Products do not affect purchasing decisions, because there are many factors that can influence consumer purchasing decisions, not only the quality of the product, but also the brand image, promotion and price. It can be concluded that the price can influence the consumer's decision to buy a product, but the price can also not affect the consumer's buying decision. This is because consumers' perceptions of prices can vary and also consumers consider the value and benefits obtained at the price paid. It can also be concluded that, promotion can influence consumer purchasing decisions, but promotion can also have no effect on consumer purchasing decisions. This could be due to the promotion that received less response from consumers, or it could also be without any promotion the customer will still buy the product because it has become a loyal customer of the product.

The brand image of the Ukhti and Munira brands does not mediate the influence of product price and promotion variables on purchasing decisions, because the brand image of Ukhti Munira is not strong enough so that it cannot influence the buying decisions of Ukhti and Munira consumers even though the company has improved its marketing mix strategy, namely improving product quality, adjusting prices increasing promotion.

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Author' Biography

Novita Ariestanty, born Tanjung Karang, Lampung, Indonesiain 17 November 1975, is a master degree student at STIE Mandala Jember and a womanpreneur in the field of fashion and business training for beginners.

He took primary and secondary education in elementary to high school in Jember, then continued his tertiary education at STIE Mandala Jember majoring in accounting. After graduating in 1998, the author spent the first 10 years as an administrative and financial office worker in various companies in Jember and in Jakarta.

In 2008 the writer quit office workers and tried to start his own business. Various communities were followed to broaden their knowledge of doing business including the TDA community (Tangan Diatas), the Emak Pintar community, the IIDB community (Ibu-Ibu Doyan Bisnis), the IIDN (Ibu-Ibu Doyan Nulis), SBO (Sekolah Bisnis Online), Bekel community (study groups), and various other business communities. In addition to joining the community, the writer also participated in various types of training both offline and online including WPC (Womanpreneur Community), the writer was a second generation IWPC alumni, Indscript alumni, SBO and Women's School (10th generation). From various experiences and business training, finally the writer has been a mentor at Indscript (a training institution) for 1 year in 2016 - 2017, and is a permanent mentor and advisor to the Bekel community (2015-now).

After five years of ups and downs in various fields of business, in 2013, the author decided to focus on the Muslim fashion business, and founded an online shop under the name La Vieta ButiQ. In addition, the author also established an online training institution named LVB Training Center, where the author is active as a mentor. To oversee the online shop business and online training, the author founded a company called Lavieta Aritama, where the author sat as its CEO.